

Education in Chemical Science and Technology

Special Volume on “Emerging Trends and Application of Green Technologies for Sustainable Development (Green Tech – 2022) ”

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PREFACE

It gives us an immense pleasure to report that the 12th volume of the periodical; “**Education in Chemical Science and Technology**” is being published jointly by Indian Chemical Society and School of Chemical, Biotechnology and Food Technology of Haldia institute of Technology (HIT Haldia) in February, 2023. This issue is consisting of papers and articles have been presented and submitted in the national conference “**Green Tech - 2022**” held at HIT Haldia. The stemmed from a stimulus to keep up the keen interests among the avid readers of the book series as well as from the researchers participated in “Green Tech- 2022”.

In the recent years, the adverse effect of drought, global warming and climate change issues are widely recognized as daunting problem facing across the globe. The devastating COVID-19 pandemic has also negatively affected lives and the world from the deadly consequences at a social, economic, and environmental level. In order to balance this crisis, there is a need to transition toward green and sustainable forms of living and practices. The National Green Technology Policy, NGTP-2009 recognized green technology as a driver to accelerate the national economy and promote sustainable development emphasizing on four focus areas of green initiatives: chemical reactions, catalysis, energy, construction materials, automobiles and hazardous waste.

Thus, Innovative green technologies are gaining snowballing attention to progress with “*Green products and Green waste*” for a sustainable future. With this view, a national conference on “***Emerging Trends and Application of Green Technologies for Sustainable Development (Green Tech - 2022)***” was organized by the School of Chemical Engineering, Biotechnology & Food Technology, Haldia Institute of Technology, during 9th-10th November, 2022 at Haldia, West Bengal, India. Many scientists, technical experts, academicians and entrepreneurs have participated in this event to share their research, idea, and experiences.

Participants of the conference have contributed their articles in this special volume to share the conference out come among a wide range of readers of the popular periodical

- *Education in Chemical Science and Technology*. This special volume includes 21 articles with versatile range of authors from different corners of India.

It starts with the first chapter on the topic "Sustainable Development – The Role of Green Technologies" (Chapter-1) written by Prof. Binay K Dutta; one of the most senior scientists of India followed by "Comparative Study on Geopolymer Coated Recycled Aggregate Concrete" (Chapter-2) by Prof. Somnath Ghosh et. al., "Green Technology and Sustainability" by Prof. Subrata Mandal et. al. Prof. Hirok Chaudhuri et.al. has discussed the use of mesoporous TiO₂ in photocatalytic reaction in their article – "A study on structural anisotropy and surface hydroxylation of nanorod units of triphase mesoporous TiO₂ for its application in photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants in wastewater"(Chapter-3). Prof. Radharani Das et. al. have beautifully represented their research on "Comparative Study of Chromium (VI) Removal by Activated Neem leave Powder and Neem Saw Dust Isotherms & Kinetics" (Chapter-4) and "Removal of Hexavalent Chromium Ion (Cr⁶⁺) from Industrial Effluents Using Low-cost Bio-Adsorbents: A Review" (Chapter-7). An interesting article, describing "A Review on Soil Strengthening using Green Waste Material" written by Ajit Kumar Paria et.al. (Chapter-5) highlights a new avenue of waste management. Aquatic pollution is serious issue, and when we talk about microplastics it become perilous. Dr. Sharmistha Bose has lucidly explained it in her article "Brief Review on Microplastic Pollution in Aquatic Body" (Chapter-6). Prof. Rajesh Das has highlighted the "Fundamentals, Limitations and Promising Future of Excitonic Solar Cell" in Chapter - 8 and with his group members he explained the "Nanostructured ZnO and TiO₂ Synthesis and Characterizations for Perovskite Solar Cell" in Chapter – 15. Chapter 9 to 11, all deal with the management of construction materials in green way. It starts with – "A study on alkali activated green binder from blended fly ash and GGBS" by prof. Ghosh et.al. (Chapter -9), followed by - "Utilization of Fly ash for Sustainable Environment Management" by Somnath Dutta et. al. (Chapter - 10), and "Performance of Laterite soil used as an adsorbent for the removal of heavy metals" by Dr. Bijoli Mondal et.al. (Chapter - 11), "Application of solar panels in vibration control of building structures" by P. Chaudhuria (Chapter - 13). Green hydrogen, hydrogen fuel and storage is an emerging field in current decades. Three review articles contributed by different group of authors, have addressed this issue in diverse facet. It starts with – "Design of Nanomaterials in Hydrogen Storage" by Prof. R. N. Jana et.al. (Chapter - 14), Hydrogen Production from Biomass: Several Routes and Current Advancements" by Keya Sau et.al. (Chapter - 16), "Production of Biodiesel and Hydrogen storage material from Chicken Feathers" by Swati Maity et.al. (Chapter - 19). Chapter - 17 deals with the "Spectroscopic study of photo-physical parameters of dyes in different solvents environment" by Prof. P. K. Khatua. Artificial photosynthesis is another interesting subject in current time. And it has been nicely explained by "Artificial Photosynthesis: Mechanism and Recent Advancement" by Sucheta Das

Maji et. al. in Chapter – 18. Safe disposal of unused drugs in pathway is a major challenge and it is been nicely explained by Swati Maiti et. al. in Chapter-19 entitled- “Toxicological Studies of Unused Paracetamol and Its Biodegradation”. The last article of this volume (Chapter – 21) entitled “The Possibility of Lithium Iodide (LiI) as H₂ Storage Material: A Conceptual DFT (CDFT) Approach” written by G. Roymahapatra et.al. deals with the different types of the hydrogen storage process, its thermochemistry, adsorption process, and binding energy in the light of the computational approach taking lithium iodide (LiI) is a viable template for hydrogen storage at low temperature.

The contents in the in this issue are expected to be appealing towards the research community in chemical sciences in holistic approach. The budding chemists are supposed to be benefitted if they thoroughly go through the research articles.

The Indian Chemical Society duly records its acknowledgement to all the authors for their contributions in this edited issue. Special thanks are conveyed to the council members and advisors for their constant adherence to the society in publishing this periodical. The editorial members from HIT, staff members of the Indian Chemical Society, and the Press are also gratefully acknowledged.

Although we have put our tireless efforts to bring out this issue in its errorless form still some inadvertent errors might have skulked in those may be apologized beforehand.

Lastly, our endeavor will be accomplished if the reader society gets interest in reading the articles critically.

Thank You !!

Radharani Das
Guest Editor
(Greem Tech-2022)

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